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IMPROVING THE PRODUCTION OF SEMI-FINISHED PRODUCTS FROM WILD PLUMS.

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Abstract: *This article consists in creating recipes of new types of semi-finished sauce-pasta products based on fruit, preparing new sauces based on them, as well as expanding the assortment of semi-finished sauce-pasta products and ready-made sauces.*

Key words: *Table salt, honey, peppermint, monosaccharides, bactericide*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ПОЛУФАБРИКАТОВ ИЗ ДИКОЙ СЛИВЫ

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Аннотация: *Данная статья заключается в создании рецептур новых видов соусов-полуфабрикатов и паст на основе фруктов, приготовлении новых соусов на их основе, а также расширении ассортимента соусов-полуфабрикатов и готовых соусов.*

Ключевые слова: *Поваренная соль, мед, мята перечная, моносахариды, бактерицид*

One of the promising directions of the industrialization of public catering is the complex supply of semi-finished products and culinary dishes of a high level of preparation.

Research in the food industry shows that it is socially and economically desirable to carry out all processes in the preparation of semi-finished products in highly mechanized production enterprises. In this case, there is an opportunity to

use the high-performance technological equipment available in the enterprises during the off-season.

Public catering enterprises achieve high efficiency when using semi-finished products: there is no need for preparation departments, the time of food preparation is reduced, and the sanitary conditions of enterprises are improved.

Currently, povidlo and compotes are mainly produced from wild plums, but the range of products made from this type of raw materials is narrow. A technology for the production of aromatic spices from wild plums is offered. Crushed coriander, red pepper and salt were used as nutritional supplements. Table salt is a preservative, kills fermenting microorganisms, mold, fungi and is an inhibitor of plum polyphenols, which preserve enzymes that change the color of the product. Coriander contains 0.2-1.6% of essential oils, as well as 16-18% of fatty acids, alkaloids, pectin, starch, proteins, sterols, steroid compounds, ascorbic acid, etc. consists of substances [1]. It is important because of the substances in its composition, especially ethers, it mainly contains linanol, which has its own properties, it stimulates appetite, improves digestion, has the properties of expelling grass and healing wounds. Coriander is recommended to be used as an antispasmodic, antiseptic and pain reliever. Red pepper is a source of vitamin C (250mg), essential oils are 0.7% to 2.6%. The sharp bitter taste is due to the presence of capsaicin alkaloid (0.5 to 1%). Red pepper is close to carrots in the amount of carotenoids. Red pepper contains flavonoids (quercetin and luteopine glycosides) that have R-vitamin activity. Due to the large amount of rutin, consumption of red pepper strengthens blood vessels and has an effective antisclerotic effect. These vitamins normalize the permeability of blood vessels, restore the elasticity of the walls, ensure the removal of cholesterol from the vessels.

In addition, all the above-mentioned nutritional supplements have a unique aroma due to the aromatic oils of red pepper and coriander. The resulting aroma is not lost even when the plum is rubbed and heat treated. Plum contains NaCl, pectin, and organic acids as components that reduce the volatility of essential oils. The ratio of components in the product is determined by organoleptic indicators. [2]

In the production of delicious wild plum sauce semi-finished products, we have chosen additives such as honey and mint. Studying the mass transfer of NaCl in plums and apricots allowed us to choose alternative modes of their processing. For plums, keeping them in 8-10% NaCl solution was enough. NaCl solution ensures that worms and larvae that may be there are released from the flesh of the

fruit, which is a factor in the safety of the finished product; Table salt acts as a preservative and inhibitor during fruit processing. Setting the concentration to 8-10% depends on the following: the use of a solution with a concentration lower than 8% requires processing the fruits for a longer time, and the fruits lose their quality due to the beginning of acetic acid fermentation of sugars; when the concentration of the solution is higher than 10%, the taste of the product is spoiled.

The selection of honey and mint as a nutritional supplement provides for the preservation of nutrients, the shape of fruits, and the creation of a new taste in the produced product.

It is known that more than 80% of carbohydrates in honey consist of monosaccharides. Honey has bactericidal and anti-inflammatory properties. The presence of phospholipids, enzymes, organic acids, and aromatic substances in it allows its use in medicinal nutrition. The addition of honey, pepper and mint powder gives the solution a unique aroma. In addition to essential oils, peppermint contains unsaturated fatty acids, thickening and adhesive substances, carotene, rutin, secondary alcohols (menthol, geraniol, carcon, etc.) and has many healing properties.

When honey solution is added to fruits, some physico-chemical changes occur in them: due to the difference in concentration of sugars in the solution, mutual diffusion of monosaccharides occurs in fruits. In addition, due to the additives in the solution, wild plum fruits become denser, which allows them to keep their shape when pouring triple kiyam.

The ratio of organic acids to raw materials in the product "Wild plum sweet sauce semi-finished products" increases from 1.3 to 2.1% due to the addition of honey, honey is rich in organic acids (amount 1.2 g) and determines the taste of the product, activates the digestive tract. New products made from wild plum contain minerals and trace elements, especially potassium-135 mg%, calcium, phosphorus, etc. rich The rich mineral composition of wild plums ensures their dietary and preventive properties.

Chemical composition of wild plum semi-finished products

Table 1

Chemical indicators	measure unit	fresh plums	Spicy and wild fragrant plum	Wild plum jam
Mass fraction:	%			
Dry matter	%	17,2	16,8	38,7
Sugar	%	10,8	10,0	32,4

Including weakened	%	6,4	6,9	24,8
Pectin	%	3,3	3,1	1,8
Organic acids	%	1,3	1,8	2,1
Kletchatka	%	0,5	0,4	0,5
Additives	%	0,07	0,04	0,08
Protein	%	0,7	0,6	0,4
β -carotene	mg/%	0,1	0,2	0,09
S vitamin	mg/%	10	6,9	4,5
Mineral substances	%	0,5	0,5	0,5
Potassium	mg/%	214	190	135
Calcium	mg/%	28	23	26
Magnesium	mg/%	17	16	15
Phosphorus	mg/%	27	21	19
Sodium	mg/%	16	17	18
Active acids	rN	3,7	4,0	3,4
Energy value per 100 g product	kKal	46,8	44,6	139,6

By studying the chemical composition of semi-finished products, it can be said that they contain S. RR and β -carotene vitamins. Vitamin C is especially abundant in spicy seasoning, as crushed red pepper is added to it, as the table confirms. rich in β -carotene. It should be noted that the amount of β -carotene doubles due to the presence of coriander in the spicy spice, the β -carotene content of coriander is close to that of carrots.

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